

Interaction of Sulphur Monochloride with Organic Compounds containing the reactive Methylene ($-\text{C}_2\text{H}_2-$) Group. Formation and Properties of Dithioketones ($\text{R}_2\text{C}:\text{S}:\text{S}$) and Dithioethers ($\text{R}_2\text{S}:\text{S}$). Part IV.

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The work described in this communication is a continuation of the work already published by one of the authors (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 379, 1231; 1922, 121, 2592). It was then suggested that sulphur monochloride appears to react in two forms:

Whereas the formation of stable dithio-compounds points to the fact that S_2Cl_2 appears to react in form (ii), it would be indeed difficult to explain the formation of mustard gas on any other assumption than that sulphur monochloride reacts in form (i) (*loc. cit.*):

As reported before the dithio-grouping resulting from the interaction of sulphur monochloride with amides of malonic ester is very stable, for the resulting di-thioketones and dithio-ethers could be easily nitrated with fuming nitric acid without affecting the dithio-grouping.

The interactions of sulphur monochloride with (1) malon-di-ethylamide, (2) malon-di-*n*-propylamide, (3) malon-di-*isobutyl*amide, (4) malon-di-*n*-heptylamide, (5) malon-di-*m*-toluidide and (6) methyl-malon-di-*m*-toluidide and (7) methyl malon-dibenzylamide were examined. Of these, malon-di-*n*-heptylamide, malon-di-*m*-toluidide and methyl-malon-dibenzylamide were prepared for the first time.

Whereas (a) compounds (1), (2), (3), (4) and (5) interacted to give dithioketones of the general formula

(b) compound (6) gave the dithio-ether of the general formula, $\text{R}\cdot\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\cdot\text{S}\cdot\text{S}\cdot\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{R}$.

and

where R may be an ethyl, propyl, isobutyl, heptyl or tolyl group.

On nitration with fuming nitric acid, the dithio-compound derived from (5) gave a tetranitro-derivative, thus:

From this, it may be suggested that the dithio-grouping in compounds of the above type, may be structurally different from that present in $\beta\beta'$ -dichlor-diethyldisulphide and such allied compounds. It also lends further support to the suggestion previously made, that sulphur monochloride may react in two forms (i) and (ii) and when it reacts in form (i), it gives rise to very stable dithio-compounds having the groupings

EXPERIMENTAL.

Interaction of Malon-diethylamide with Sulphur Monochloride.—Malon-diethylamide was prepared by Whiteley's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 366) by the condensation of ethylmalonate (16 g.) with ethylamine (30 g. of 33 per cent solution). It was crystallised from benzene, m. p. 149°.

Malondiethylamide (2 g.) was put in a flask with 30 c.c. of dry benzene. Sulphur monochloride (2 g.) was added to it, and the flask was refluxed on a sand-bath for three hours. Hydrogen chloride began to evolve moderately on heating. Within 15 minutes, a solid separated, and bumping began which had to be controlled. The solid was separated by filtering the solution at the pump, and was washed with dry petroleum to remove the adhering sulphur monochloride.

It is very soluble in acetone, ethylacetate, acetic acid and chloroform; less so in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, benzene and toluene; sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide and ether, and insoluble in petroleum. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol. It shrinks at 186° and melts at 202°. (Found: N, 12·97; S, 29·46. $C_7H_{14}N_2O_2S_2$ requires N, 12·73; S, 29·09 per cent.).

Malon-di-n-propylamide and Sulphur Monochloride.—Malon-di-n-propylamide was prepared by Whiteley's method (*loc. cit.*). Ethylmalonate (9·5 g.) and n-propylamine were taken in a sealed tube and, after 24 hours, were heated at 125°—130° for six hours. The mixture solidified when allowed to remain at the ordinary temperature for some hours. The sealed tube was then opened, and the white solid was washed with petroleum. The m. p. of the substance, purified from benzene was 139°.

The above amide (5 g.) was condensed with sulphur monochloride (5 g.) in a similar way.

The product is very soluble in chloroform, benzene, ethylacetate, acetone, acetic acid and nitrobenzene; less so in ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol and toluene; sparingly soluble in carbon bisulphide and ether; and insoluble in water and petroleum. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol. It shrinks at 172° and melts at 180°. (Found: N, 10·92; S, 25·69. $C_6H_{10}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 11·29; S, 25·80 per cent.).

Malon-di-isobutylamide and Sulphur Monochloride.—Malon-di-isobutylamide was prepared in the same way as malon-di-n-propylamide, by condensing ethylmalonate (8 g.) with isobutylamine (7·3 g.). The product was crystallised from benzene and melted at 126°.

The above amide (2 g.) and sulphur monochloride (1·5 g.) were condensed as in the previous cases.

The white product so obtained dissolves readily in chloroform, acetic acid, ethylacetate, or nitrobenzene; less readily in benzene, toluene, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and acetone; sparingly so in ether, carbon bisulphide, or carbon tetrachloride, and is insoluble in hot water or light petroleum. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol. It shrinks at 196° and melts at 202°. (Found: N, 10·43; S, 22·98. $C_{11}H_{20}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 10·14; S, 23·19 per cent.).

Preparation of Malon-di-n-heptylamide.—A mixture of *n*-heptylamine (11·5 g.) and ethylmalonate (8 g.) was allowed to remain in a sealed tube at the ordinary temperature for 24 hours, when it was found in a semi-solid condition. The sealed tube was then heated in a paraffin bath at 125-130° for about 7 hours. The tube was opened when cool, and the white solid was taken out and washed with petroleum. The solid thus obtained was practically pure, and weighed 12 g.

It dissolves very readily in chloroform, benzene, toluene, ethylacetate, acetic acid, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone, and nitrobenzene; less readily in carbon tetrachloride and ether; and is sparingly soluble in petroleum, and insoluble in water. It crystallises from benzene and melts at 132°. (Found: N, 9·52. $C_{17}H_{34}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 9·40 per cent.).

Malon-di-n-heptylamide and Sulphur Monochloride.—Malon-di-n-heptylamide (3 g.) was condensed with sulphur monochloride (1·5 g.) in the usual manner. The resulting substance, being very soluble in benzene, was precipitated by petroleum. It came out as a gelatinous white mass which was filtered and washed with dry petroleum.

It is very soluble in benzene, chloroform, acetic acid, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone, ethyl acetate and nitrobenzene; less soluble in toluene and carbon bisulphide; and sparingly soluble in ether, petroleum, and carbon tetrachloride. It was purified from alcohol, m. p. 125°. (Found: N, 7·83; S, 17·37. $C_{17}H_{34}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 7·77; S, 17·77 per cent.).

Malon-di-m-toluidide and Sulphur Monochloride.—The amide (2 g.) and sulphur monochloride (1 g.) were condensed as in the previous cases.

The product is readily soluble in chloroform, acetic acid, ethylacetate, acetone and nitrobenzene; less readily in benzene, toluene, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, carbon tetrachloride and carbon

bisulphide; sparingly soluble in ether and hot water, and insoluble in light petroleum. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol. It shrinks at 158° and melts at 180° to a yellow liquid. (Found: S, 18·13. $C_{11}H_8O_2N_2S_2$ requires S, 18·60 per cent.).

Nitration.—One gram of the above substance was added in a conical flask to 10 c.c. of fuming nitric acid (d 1·5). The flask was heated on a sand-bath until the evolution of oxides of nitrogen slackened. The flask was allowed to cool, when a little yellow solid came down. As the solid was too little to be filtered through the asbestos, the solution was added to some distilled water in a beaker. The precipitated solid was filtered at the pump, washed with distilled water, and allowed to dry at the ordinary temperature and powdered. The powder was dried in an air oven at 60-70°. It melts with decomposition at 166°. (Found: N, 16·32; S, 12·27. $C_{11}H_{11}O_1N_2S_2$ requires N, 16·03; S, 12·21 per cent.).

Methyl malon-di-m-toluidide.—Methylmalonic ester (10 g.) was condensed with *m*-toluidine (18 g.) in the same way as in the case of the corresponding malon-derivative. The temperature, in this case, was raised to 280°. The yield was very poor.

It is very soluble in benzene, toluene, chloroform, acetic acid, ethylacetate, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone and nitrobenzene; less readily in carbon tetrachloride, and insoluble in petroleum. It was crystallised from benzene, *m. p.* 157°. (Found: N, 9·86. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9·46 per cent.).

Methyl malon-di-m-toluidide and Sulphur Monochloride.—The above amide (2 g.) and sulphur monochloride (0·5 g.) were condensed together in the usual manner. The reaction in this case was slower than in the case of the corresponding malon-di-*m*-toluidide derivative.

The white product is readily soluble in ethylacetate, acetic acid, acetone and nitrobenzene; less readily soluble in benzene, toluene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol; slightly soluble in carbon bisulphide, ether and hot water and insoluble in petroleum. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol, *m. p.* 187°-188°. (Found: S, 9·39. $C_{22}H_{22}O_2N_2S_2$ requires S, 9·78 per cent.).

Methylmalon-di-benzylamide.—Ethylmethylmalonate (9 g.) and benzylamine (11 g.) were taken in a round bottomed flask and heated

at 150-160° as in the case of other amides. The white product so obtained readily dissolves in benzene, toluene, chloroform, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone, ethylacetate, acetic acid and nitrobenzene; less readily in chloroform, and is sparingly soluble in carbon bisulphide, ether, petroleum and hot water. It was purified from benzene, m. p. 142°. (Found: N, 9.66. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.46 per cent.).

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